

THE CONTRIBUTION OF MODERN ENGLISH WRITERS TO THE GENRE OF ANIMALISM IN THE LITERATURE

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Abstract: The present paper is about an English animalistic fairy tale. In the second part of the twentieth century, the issue of how animals are depicted in literature becomes the most intensively researched. In recent decades, a new branch of scientific inquiry known as "human-animal studies" has emerged in English literature. Sociology, history, literary criticism, ethnology, law, and other fields connected to the complicated interaction between man and animals are included. As a result, a considerable number of research on the role of animal imagery in literary works have been published in recent years. They reflect various points of view and pertain to various topics of animal literature.

Key: Hugh Lofting, T.S. Eliot, Gerald Durrell, The Story of Dr. Doolittle, English children's literature, elitist literature, Terry Pratchett, J. Rowling, Fantastic Beasts and Where to Find Them, mockumentary, animal images, English animalistic tale.

An important role in the formation of fairy tale literature about animals was played by a series of books about Dr. Doolittle by Hugh Lofting (1920-1936)³⁵ are both humans and animals. They play the same role in storytelling and create an atmosphere of all-consuming love for nature and all her creatures. Despite the fact that the animals in the work can talk, they behave like representatives of the natural world and face specific animal problems. It's connected with the profession of the protagonist, Dr. Doolittle is a doctor who treats animals. In this work, we are faced with the development of image tradition characteristic of English children's literature non-existent animals (for example, Push-Pull, when creating an image in which a popular children's toy is used), but they are shown as real-life animals with all their inherent biological characteristics. The sociocultural context must also be taken into account. For example, Dr. Doolittle's particular attitude towards suffering, which brought the war: H. Lofting invented the story of a doctor of animals, so as not to tell your children

³⁵ Hugh John Lofting (14 January 1886 – 26 September 1947) was an English author trained as a civil engineer, who created the classic children's literature character of Doctor Doolittle.

the whole terrible truth about the war. But still, the military realities deeply hidden in the form of a literary fairy tale are present and here. Let in the first book of Lofting's journey Dr. Doolittle never bring him to the battlefield, but the animals he heals in these wanderings, in some way embody the suffering of those animals, who died at the front.

In his works, H. Lofting creates a special language of animals, which can be learned by Sims who love and understand animals. An introduction to the narrative fabric of animal language is very important in the context of the development of British animalism. Animals are not like humans, but on the contrary, a person after the application of certain efforts can understand animals. Thus, there is a decrease in the anthropomorphic beginning which emphasizes the difference between animals and humans. Despite the fact that Dr. Doolittle himself is a doctor by profession, and not a veterinarian, his love for animals and the desire to protect them occupy an important place in the cycle of fairy tales. H. Lofting sought to create a new, non-anthropocentric system of moral guidelines in an era when humanity has clearly lost its own moral compass. For example, "The Story of Dr. Doolittle" uses such a technique as looking at the world of people through the eyes of the animal, which makes it possible to more clearly express the inhumane aspects of human behavior: the most important episodes are manifestations of reckless cruelty in the actions of the African king Jolliginka, the Barbary pirates, etc.

It is also necessary to the work of T.S. Eliot "Popular Cat Science" by Old Possum (1939), which is worth a part of the work of the modernist poet. T.S. Eliot creates a kind of poetic encyclopedia of feline Britain, in which he shows different types of cats, their habitats, habits, etc. The author explains the reasons for the behavior of pets, and talks about complex relationships both with people and within animal society.

In the second half of the 20th century, both fiction and non-fiction literature about animals. Explosion in the development of art-documentary genres in the second half of the 20th century greatly influenced animal literature. Many zoologists, naturalists and ethologists began to publish their works, related to their experience with animals. Significant breakthrough in the study of ethology, animal behavior begins to be explained not only by the laws of heredity but also by certain social regularities. Science convincingly proves that animals have thought, communication (both within their species and with representatives of another), an established society. A new branch of science is emerging sociobiology, which explains all these patterns; also formed a new direction in the humanities —human-animal studies, already mentioned in the introduction to this work. Writers turn to traditional theme of animal-human interaction, drawing attention to new unusual aspects. Now man seeks to understand animals, to carry out an act of mutual communication. An important role begins to play

in environmental issues. Writers call on their readers to think about how civilization affects the natural world and how negative impacts can be mitigated.

The most representative in this respect seems to us the works of Gerald Durrell (1925-1995) and James Harriot (1916- 1995), which will be the subject of one of the chapters of this study. Both these authors, not being professional by their first professional writers, created a huge number of works dedicated to relationships between animals and people. J. Durrell as a famous naturalist and animal rights activist raises in his work the question of people's responsibility for the conservation of endangered species flora and fauna. J. Harriot approaches this issue from a different angle. Based on his experience as a veterinarian, he depicts in his works the realities of directly British reality, while speaking of human responsibility for the natural world that surrounds him.

Many writers whose work is not directly related to the animal image quite often refer to this topic in some of their works, and this tendency can be found in both "high", and in popular literature. In this case, writers not only create a picture of an idyllic relationship between man and animal, and based on close observation of animal representatives' world, resulting in a history of complex mutual communication. On the one hand, there are many stories about pets, so-called "pet stories", where the authors describe their experiences of communication and interaction with their wards, while these works constitute a separate layer of mass literature (a series of books about a cat Bob J. Bowen).

On the other hand, even well-known representatives of the "elitist literature" refer to the image of domestic animals. One of the examples includes Doris Lessing's collection *Cats* (2002), based on several collections of autobiographical stories (1967-2000). The writer describes her life surrounded by cats, starting with a childhood spent on a South African farm. Cats for Doris Lessing are highly intelligent creatures that are capable of human interaction. The author observes two cats (gray and black), their interaction and competition, and comes to the conclusion that cats have their own complex language that humans can learn to understand and interpret. The life of cats is no less complicated than human life: the author draws parallels between the laws of survival in the world of animals and the human world. On the other side of the literary scale is the wonderful science fiction writer, Terry Pratchett, known for his numerous works about the Discworld. T. Pratchett creates a kind of humorous encyclopedia of cats in English literature titled "Cat Without Fools" (1989). This work presents numerous types of cats, their habitats, interests, and habits. The story is filled with a variety of comical situations, associated with the unexpected behavior of cats and the reaction of their owners. The writer simultaneously continues and parodies the

traditions of the famous poet T.S. Eliot and his “Popular Science of Cats, written by Old Possum.”

The most popular British writer J. Rowling too refers to the traditions of literature about animals and creates her own version of medieval bestiary – “Fantastic Beasts and Where to Find Them” (2001)³⁶.

One of the latest trends in animal literature is the emergence of the mockumentary genre. This term is made up of two words: — to mock (fake, mock) and —documentary (a documentary piece of art). The term appeared in the 1950s in the USA and was used to define the genre of satirical television journalism. This genre is characterized by imitation of documentaries, falsification, and mystification. Recently the term has begun used in literary criticism. This form is a parody stylization of artistic and documentary narration, for example, a biography, with all the works inherent in this kind of sign. The book “Uggie. My story”³⁷ was published in 2012, it is an autobiographical story trained by Jack Russell Terrier, famous for his roles in the films “Water for Elephants” and “The Artist” allegedly recorded by journalist Wendy Holden. The author shows well-known phenomena, for example, the process of making a film, from the point of view of an animal. Ugg “tell” about their real-life human colleagues, maintaining a special canine attitude to life and events³⁸.

Also in the second half of the 20th century, there was a revival of interest to literary fairy tales about animals, active use begins this form, which continues to this day. Continues to develop both a fairy tale about animals and directly an animalistic fairy tale. As an example of a fairy tale about animals, one can cite the work of Donald Bisset (1910-1995) (“Talks with a Tiger”, “The Adventures of Yak”, “The Adventures of Mandy Duck”, “The adventures of uncle Tick Tock and other stories”, “The story of Smokey Horse”, “Journey to the Jungle” The main characters of his short tales for small children are animals that lead a life similar to human. The anthropomorphic beginning in the fairy tales of D. Bisset definitely prevails: the tiger mother bakes pies, the hippo likes to eat cookies in beds, etc. Approximately also animal characters in fairy tales are depicted in E. Hogarth’s (1910-1993) “The Adventures of Mafin the Donkey and His Friends”. Such an interpretation of animal images is primarily associated with the profession of both D. Bisset and E. Hogarth. Both writers worked

³⁶ This book first appeared as one of the textbooks in the Harry Potter books. Later, J. Rowling decided to release it as a separate book for a better understanding of the realities of the magical world by readers.

³⁷ Holden W. Ugg. My life. – M.: Eksmo, 2014. – 256 p.

³⁸ Separate features of this genre were encountered in literature before. As an example, we can cite the works of J. K. Jerome (Jerome. J. K. If only we had tails! // Collected works in 3 volumes. - M.: Art. - 1996. - T. 3. - P. 28-32), K. Chapek (Chapek K. From the point of view of a cat // Collected works in 5 volumes. - M.: State publishing house of fiction. - 1958. - T. 1 - P. 467471). Chemberdzh (Chemberdzh V.N. Dog life. - M.: Astrel, 2012. - 384 p.). At the same time, it is in “Ugg. My Life” is not only told from the point of view of an animal, but the animal is already on the cover as the author of the work, which contributes to the comic effect.

for television, and initially, their works were created as scripts for children's entertainment programs.

An English animalistic tale of this period is presented with such names as R. Adams (1920-2016) and G. Kilworth (b. 1941). Writers emphasize the importance of the natural science component in the creation of their works, based on the works of naturalists when creating animal images. Animal characters don't act like humans but behave according to their animal nature. In the third chapter of this dissertation research, we turn to a more detailed analysis animalistic tale of this period. Animal images are an integral part of the literary process throughout its development. We can distinguish two main directions in the literature about animals: fiction and documentaries that develop in parallel throughout the literary process. Since the second half of the 19th century, we can observe a tendency towards their merging, which most clearly manifests itself in the literature of the second half of the 20th century.

By the second half of the twentieth century, gradually a separate direction in the literature about animals crystallizes. Writers, relying on the traditions of English literature on the one hand, and scientific discoveries in the field of sociobiology, on the other hand, create works in which the images of animals receive a different interpretation. This type of literature was definitely influenced by phenomena such as cult nature among romantic poets, interest in the natural sciences in the Victorian era, the traditions of the literary fairy tale of the "golden age" of English children's literature, J. London's social Darwinism.

The combination of a scientific approach to creating the image of an animal, and images of the beast as part of the natural world with techniques characteristic of fiction gives us reason to apply the definition of animation to literature. Literary work related to this direction should contain a synthesis of scientific and artistic beginnings. Animals begin to be depicted based on their biological nature, which emphasizes the connection with the natural sciences' knowledge. The main conflict for animalistic works there is a conflict between nature and civilization (the world of animals and the world of people), which writers solve in a new way, referring to topical issues of environmental protection. For English animalistic, the second half of the 20th century is characterized by the use of images of animals to depict complex relationships between human and natural communities. The interaction between man and the natural world remains in the focus of interest of writers, but this conflict gets a new interpretation. Writers seek to understand the natural being, to explain the motivation of certain biological actions. English animalism of the second half of the 20th century manifests itself in memoir genres and in literary fairy tales. Most brightly this is demonstrated in the work of G. Orwell, T. Hughes, W. Faulkner, and T. S. Eliot, whose works will be the subject of analysis of the study.

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